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The Covid-19 Pandemic Impacts on Apprentices' Occupational Health in Western Switzerland: Between Invisibilisation of Their Status and Ordinary Suffering

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Abstract

Vocational education and training (VET) plays an important role in Switzerland. The dual system directly confronts apprentices with real working conditions and societal context, such as the COVID-19 pandemic. Considering the limitation of the vast literature that apprehends the young workers' OHS through the lens of age and adolescent risk taking, this paper examines the impact of "apprentice status" on OHS during the pandemic. The examination of the federal and cantonal policies concerning apprentices during the pandemic highlights the apprentices' dual status as young workers and learners. This paper, then, shows that the potential consequences of this dual status on the apprentices' OHS during the pandemic are evacuated by the political and media discourses. Now, the use of five group interviews with apprentices (painters, hairdressers, retail professionals, healthcare assistants) highlights how much their suffering during the pandemic is inextricably linked to their particular status, considering their professional sector and company. Yet, the conversation shows that the apprentices' experience during the pandemic reveal an ordinary and silent suffering.

Keywords

apprentices, occupational health, pandemic Covid-19, suffering, dual training

1 Context

Vocational education and training (VET) plays an important role in Switzerland. VET is the most popular training pathway after leaving compulsory school, with two thirds of young people following this route, most often in its dual form (State Secretariat for Education, Research and Innovation [SERI], 2022). The dual system, which combines theoretical training in vocational schools and practical learning in companies, directly confronts apprentices with real working conditions and societal context, such as the COVID-19 pandemic.

Although on-the-job training can be an opportunity for professional and personal development, the Swiss official statistics on young workers that include apprentices indicate that their professional activity can affect their health and integrity in the short and long term (Federal statistical office [FSO], 2021). They are exposed to significant risks to their physical health (exposure to chemical substances, noise, vibrations, etc.) and psychological health (overload, stress, harassment, etc.). One study shows that the pandemic has had a considerable impact on adolescents' mental health (Prince & Barrense-Dias, 2021). Despite this pronounced vulnerability, no national statistical survey has yet provided information on COVID impacts on apprentices' health specifically.

This contribution examines the pandemic impacts on apprentices' occupational health (OHS) and how it brings to the fore the relevance of taking their status into account when dealing with occupational health.

2 Approach

The international literature generally starts from a twofold observation. On the one hand, young workers (Breslin & Smith, 2005) and apprentices (FSO, 2021; Rasmussen et al., 2011) are more likely to be victims of accidents than adult workers and students. On the other hand, they are exposed from an early age to a work environment that is potentially dangerous for their physical and mental health.

While the majority of the literature apprehends the young workers' OHS through the lens of age and adolescent risk taking, it "now seems to be established that short job tenure and workplace factors predict occupational injury more than age or other individual factors" (Grytnes, 2021, p. 1). In this perspective, some studies using qualitative methods adopt a perspective aimed at capturing the impact of "apprentice status" on OHS.

These studies, which are few, consider that the ambivalent status of apprentices, simultaneously employees and learners, partly explains their greater vulnerability. Indeed, being an apprentice means occupying a special position in the social division of labour. Apprentices as novices have a subordinate status within the professional hierarchy and the work group (Duc & Lamamra, 2022 ; Raykov & Taylor, 2013). As young workers, they are also more subject to physical and organisational constraints, depending on the company size and the training trade (Denave & Renard, 2019; Gervais et al., 2006; Ledoux et al., 2008). Their subordinate status gives them little room for manoeuvre in the performance of their work, sometimes confining them to repetitive, monotonous, or even dangerous tasks. They also show an inclination to submit to the requirements, social norms and injunctions existing in the work group (Grytnes, 2018 ; Raykov & Taylor, 2013). This can lead them to adopt costly attitudes and gestures affecting their health. Apprentices are also precariously inserted into the work group. Their presence within the company (between 2 and 4 years, during a few days per week) remains temporary. However, this precarious status influences their integration as well as the possibility of health knowledge transmission.

Thus, a systematic review of the international literature allows us to shift the focus from an individual centred approach on apprentices' OHS to a sociological and organisational one. This paper therefore examine the effects of apprentice status in four sectors (care, painting, hairdressing, sales) on the way in which apprentices were confronted with the effects of

COVID. To do this, we first study the policy measures implemented for apprentices during the pandemic as well as the media and political treatment of their situation. Secondly, the group interviews conducted with the apprentices are analysed in order to show how they experienced this period. In conclusion, the impacts of apprentice status on their experiences during the pandemic are discussed.

3 Methods

This contribution is based on a work in progress on apprentices' OHS in the French part of Switzerland. The analysis is based on a documentary corpus and five group interviews.

The corpus of documents is composed of press articles. Two local newspapers (*24 heures*, *Le Temps*) selected in this study have a wide readership in the French-speaking part of Switzerland, where our research takes place. This selection could be completed by other daily newspapers of the French-speaking Switzerland. The corpus results from a keyword search in both newspapers' online archives. Only articles dealing with youth (students, apprentices, young people) during the pandemic were selected (N=48). The corpus of documents also includes the measures and positions taken by political authorities and professional organisations. This contribution refers to three types of documents: the federal and cantonal ordinances on measures to tackle the coronavirus, the website and reports of the Swiss Confederation's "Apprenticeship Perspective" task force, and finally, the report of the Swiss Employers' Union (UPS) and the Swiss Union of Arts and Crafts (USAM).

Finally, the analysis of the apprentices' experience is based on five group interviews (see Table 1) conducted with six painters, eight hairdressers, five retail professionals and two groups of six healthcare assistants.

Chart 1

Participants in group interviews by occupation, canton and type of company

<i>Apprenticeship</i>	<i>Region</i>	<i>Number of participants</i>	<i>M</i>	<i>W</i>	<i>Non binary</i>	<i>Type of company</i>	<i>Group interview numbers</i>
Painters	Valais	6	3	2	1	Small to medium sized companies	1
Hairdressers	Fribourg	8	1	7		Hairdressing salons	2
Retail professionals	Vaud	5	4	1		Garden center (1), sportshop (1), food store (2), clothes and furniture store (1)	3
Healthcare assistants	Geneva	6	1	5		Retirement home (1), homecare (4), hospital (1)	4
Healthcare assistants	Geneva	6	0	6		Retirement home (2), homecare (2), hospital (2)	5

The semi-structured interviews conducted between October and December 2022 focused globally on issues of mental and physical health in the workplace of apprentices. The effects of the COVID on the health of apprentices were therefore not the central focus of the interviews. As such, the analyses presented in this contribution are exploratory in nature. They make it possible to raise avenues and questions that deserve to be explored through the production of new material.

4 Findings

4.1 Supporting the apprenticeship market first and foremost

The restrictions decided by the Confederation to cope with the pandemic indirectly inform on the apprentices' general situation. Different measures (closures and cessation of activity, teleworking, conditional openings) took place successively or simultaneously and affected the sectors of activity in different ways (see Table A in the appendix). While students were confined and working remotely, the vast majority of apprentices went to work. Indeed, the monitoring indicates that 64% of apprentices were going to work in April 2020 and 91% in July (Bolli et al., n.d.). However, the attendance of apprentices at their workplaces varies greatly from one sector to another. Within the retail sector, only essential shops remained open all the time. Hospitals, retirement homes and home care staff never stopped working. However, hospital caregivers (including trainers) were sometimes transferred to the COVID unit, which reduced the number of staff in the other departments.

In this context, the federal authorities adopted measures to ensure the smooth functioning of the VET system and to promote the creation of new apprenticeship positions. The federal task force "Apprenticeship Perspective" was created in May 2020 in response to Art. 20 of the Labor Law (LTr). It plans to correct "the imbalances that have occurred or threaten to occur in the initial vocational training market" during the pandemic. To achieve this, the task force set up a special fund to "provide targeted support [...] for projects by the cantons, labour organisations and associations aimed at maintaining, creating and filling apprenticeship positions" (Task Force "Prospects for Apprenticeship", 2021, p.13). The cantons' intervention is essentially part of this federal framework. The cantons in French-speaking Switzerland mainly use the premium for hiring an apprentice and the co-financing of training companies' networks (see Table B in the appendix).

The decisions taken by the federal authorities with regard to apprentices are part of a policy to promote training during the pandemic. These decisions give some indications of their special status during this period. First of all, the apprentices' legal status in terms of OHS is defined by the ordinance on "young workers" in accordance with the Labour Law (LTr). During the pandemic, young workers are not included among the "vulnerable persons" (pregnant women, persons suffering from certain pathologies or genetic abnormalities) for whom the Confederation enacted additional protective measures in April 2020. As young workers, apprentices did not benefit from measures to reduce their workloads and working hours or from measures to strengthen training support. As for the other categories of workers, the employer was nevertheless obliged to respect the prevention measures defined by the Federal Office of Public Health (mask, disinfection, reduction of contact with clients and colleagues, quarantine, etc.).

Secondly, compared to most other categories of workers, apprentices were only eligible for financial compensation (reduced working hours or 'RHT') at certain times of the year during the pandemic. These were received by companies when working hours were reduced, and only in the event of forced closure (Travail.Suisse, n.d.). This decision aims to keep apprentices at work in order to guarantee the normal continuation of their training in the company and their integration into the labour market. Thus, it appears that the special status of apprentices (between employees and trainees) had led to differential treatment compared to other categories of workers. This treatment confronts apprentices with working and training conditions altered by prevention measures, restrictions and staff reductions. This potentially exposes them to increased workload, stress and risks.

Finally, the measures concerning vocational training certification, and their comparison with those created for gymnasium students, show that apprentices have, in certain aspects and to a certain extent, benefited from student status. Like students, apprentices were subjected to

distance learning (by cantonal decision) for theoretical courses between March and June 2021, depending on the canton. In addition, the ordinances provided for the abolition of theoretical examinations for all apprentices and the possibility of waiving practical tests. The choice of one of the three possible variants (maintaining practical exams in the company, taking exams in a centralised examination centre, or having the trainer assess the experience gained in the company) is left to labour organisations. In comparison, the cantonal authorities that set the validation procedures for gymnasium students maintained written examinations and replaced oral examinations with written ones. This highlights the apprentices' dual status, who were both young workers subject to the COVID rules applied to adult workers, and learners for whom measures relatively identical to those applied to students were applied for examinations.

These COVID policy measures are intended to support the apprenticeship market and ensure timely completion of training. More generally, they are part of a broader policy aiming to maintain the "usual conditions" of VET (SERI, n.d.). As such, it is fully in line with the concerns of the professional organisations, in particular those of the UPS and the USAM. On the one hand, the latter were concerned about the loss of qualifications that would result from overly strict measures, since they would compromise the acquisition of skills based on face-to-face training at the three learning sites (training company, vocational school, inter-company courses) (Taddei, 2021). On the other hand, employers and professional organisations were concerned about the lack of new recruits in some sectors, which the pandemic could have further exacerbated if the examination and promotion schedule was postponed by several months. In their report on VET during the pandemic, the UPS and USAM were pleased to note that in some sectors (agri-food, construction) affected by the shortage of labour "it has almost been possible to work normally" (UPS & UPSAM, n.d., p.3). For their part, the cantonal and federal authorities were pleased with the results obtained, namely the very low rate of apprenticeship breakdowns and the high rate of successful transition to the labour market in comparison with European countries (OECD, 2021). By doing so, the Task Force report considers that the VET system as it exists, i.e. with the usual boundaries of public-private partnership (SERI, 2022), have proved its worth during the pandemic. According to the report "any state intervention in the VET system in the event of an economic crisis should therefore be avoided" (Task Force "Perspectives Apprentissage", 2021, p.16).

4.2 The media erasure of apprentices' suffering

The concerns of this training policy were widely reported in the local general press. Two thirds of the articles in the daily newspapers *Le Temps* and *24 heures* mentioning apprentices during the pandemic dealt with their situation from the point of view of apprenticeship positions and their training recognition (see graph below).

Graph 1

Number of articles by themes and newspapers

Only a few articles mention the apprentices' experience. An article in *24 heures* (Collet & Ebinger, 2023) reveals a discrepancy between the views reported by apprentices and those of certain training professionals:

The director [of the training centre] believes that the pandemic is having less of an impact than expected. "The situation is under control, says the deputy director [of the training centre]. We are surprised by the ability of young people to adapt" (...). The teaching staff is more cautious: "The students complain a lot in class, says a teacher at the vocational school. They are tired, unmotivated and have difficulty concentrating, because of the mask, but also because of the tensions they feel at school and in the workplace". This was echoed by our three [interviewed apprentices].

In this example, the training centre management moderates the negative effects of the pandemic, underlining later the normal rate of success in the exams and the good progress of the apprenticeship, while some teachers mention the difficulties and sufferings endured by some of the apprentices.

The other articles consulted deal more extensively with the suffering of young people (depression, social isolation, anxiety, etc.). This media treatment tends to make invisible the part played by the working and training conditions in companies during the pandemic in the suffering of apprentices. Moreover, it erases the variable effects of the pandemic on their situations and potentially on apprentices' health depending on the professional sector. For example, retail professional apprentices in some sales sectors were assigned to work at home due to store closures, while healthcare assistants' apprentices were heavily involved in the care of COVID patients throughout the pandemic. These elements are addressed in the analysis of the group interviews with apprentices.

4.3 Contrasting experiences revealing ordinary suffering

The interviews conducted with apprentices show the pandemic impacts on their training and working conditions, as well as its effect on their health. These impacts are expressed very differently depending on the sector and the type of workplace. However, apprentices do not only associate their suffering with the pandemic context. Indeed, they do not talk at length about COVID, unlike other topics related to their ordinary condition as apprentices.

First of all, healthcare assistant apprentices in home care did not always have the appropriate protective equipment. For example, the masks provided did not meet the protection standard required during the pandemic (FFP2), mainly due to supply problems. In addition, some of them talk about having only one mask available for the whole day. In hospitals, apprentices reported a heavy workload and limited training and supervision, as the trainer was often required to work in other departments. Furthermore, both apprentices in retirement home, home care and hospitals stated that they had been more exposed to patients' suffering and death. Their words also show that they face a collective defence strategy according to which being a 'health professional' implies showing empathy without expressing emotions too strongly:

Estelle: Deaths, deaths, we've experienced... Well people dying and it was not easy for us. I think that in this class there are several of us who have seen deaths, it was not always easy.

(...)

Sylvia: They'll tell you "Ah, but you'll get used to it".

Camille: Yeah, that's it. "Yeah, it's the first one who hurts, then you'll see"

[interview n°4]

We can assume that this defensive strategy (Dejours, 1998) is more difficult to internalise for apprentices as professional socialisation is part of a long-term process. Its success depends partly on integration into the work group. However, their comments on their training conditions in an ordinary context (outside of the pandemic) indicate that they do not really feel that they belong to the work group.

Paul: There are weeks like this, one or two people are missing...

Amélie: We count when it suits them.

(...)

Camille: And for them, we're there to fill in the gaps

[interview n°5].

The feeling of being treated as "cheap" labour seems to be an obstacle to integration into the work group. We hypothesise that this lack of integration contributes to the feeling of having to face, without any real support, situations such as the pandemic for which they were not prepared. Indeed, they have not yet integrated strategies to deal with death, stress and suffering at the lowest cost. The suffering that results from this situation is reflected when they say that they are not really heard and supported in their ordinary work. Lucie who has been trained in the COVID unit for several months makes a mockery of the compulsory visits to the psychologist set up specifically during the pandemic:

Lucie: I've been in the acute COVID unit for three years now, so we had to go to the COVID psychologist.

Interviewer: Was that an instruction ?

Lucie: It was an instruction.

Interviewer: And was it a positive thing for you, did it help you?

Lucie: No, it was like thirty minutes, it was basic and trivial questions, so that's it.

Aurélie: Just to say that they are psychologically monitored in the unit, that's all.

[Interview 4]

Thus, experiencing a lack of support and listening from the hierarchy (including from trainers) during ordinary training resulted in a distancing, or even a rejection of this ad hoc measure during the pandemic. This measure also appears mismatched with the suffering experienced and is unable to respond to the lack of supervision.

Among retail professional apprentices, the pandemic experience varies according to the type of workplace. For some, like Pedro who is doing his apprenticeship in the food industry, managing the shop with a reduced number of staff and sometimes dealing with nervous customers lead to increased pressure:

Pedro: We weren't even 10 [employees] in the shop, we have 200 people in the shop. It's... It was quite complicated. And when there were too many people, well, we had to block people. And there were [customers] who didn't like it. And, especially us, well, we're younger than... for example, fathers who think they're strong enough because we're young. And they start to... Raising their voices and stuff like that, so it's a bit annoying. Especially as they used to put us in front all the time, so... (laughs)

[Interview 3]

However, others say that they have well experienced the pandemic in terms of customer management. Fernando, for instance, who is doing his apprenticeship in a sports shop (non-essential trade), explains that the restrictions involving distance selling (ordering, depot-selling, etc.) offered him a greater flexibility to meet customers demand:

Fernando: I loved it. I really liked it! Because... you don't have that negative side of selling, where sometimes you have all the customers at the same time and then for 1-2 hours you have nothing, and then it's all at once again. Well, there you managed your time as you wanted.

[Interview 3]

As Fernando points out, the measures against the pandemic have sometimes made it possible to reduce the workload and the tensions which retail professional apprentices are sometimes subjected to, particularly with the trainers and hierarchy. Retail professional apprentices talk at length about their ordinary suffering. They mention in particular the fatigue generated by the long working hours, including evenings and weekends, and particularly during Christmas, to which is added the burden of school work. Therefore, some apprentices report that they benefited from a relief when the shops were closed or when there were fewer customers in the shop.

For hairdressers, it was above all the mask wearing that made the work difficult:

Audrey: It was more when we wore the masks, because wearing the masks with the heat... At least we were protected from the products, but with the heat, it was awful!

Mathilde: Yeah, it was horrible.

[Unidentified participant]: The ears...

[Another unidentified participant]: On the sides it hurts!

(...)

Maëlle: You couldn't see anything, it makes pimples pop, it was hot... and breathing especially.

[Interview 2]

In addition to face mask discomfort, there were other sufferings, often trivialised, caused by the uncomfortable postures and the injunctions of appearance standards at work (Denave & Renard,

2019). The heat was more difficult to bear as the ventilation of the hairdressing premises, recommended during the COVID, was not always possible or came up against the clients' comfort:

Morgan: For example, we realise that it's time to open because there's a cloud of hairspray in the salon. We open the door a little bit and it's like, "Oh, it's cold"! In the summer, there's no problem, but in the winter, it becomes complicated to open the door [without disturbing the customers]

Anita: It's a bit complicated because I work in a shopping centre. It's air-conditioned, but there are no windows.

[Interview 2]

Here again, the customers decrease during the pandemic reduced the regular workload. In this regard, the hairdresser apprentices emphasised the stress caused by the continuous flow of hurried customers which forced them not to systematically respect basic protective measures, such as wearing gloves when using dye products.

Anita: If you're stressed, if there's a client in between waiting for you, you're not going to think: "Oh, I've got to put on a mask to do this." It has to be done quickly. So we don't necessarily think about it.

[Interview 2]

In this sense, the closure of the salons was sometimes experienced as a moment of respite.

Finally, the experience of painters' apprentices is quite different. Indeed, these apprentices continued to work under ordinary conditions, although the employer had an obligation to ensure that prevention measures were respected as indicated above. However, their comments reveal the unrealistic nature of these COVID measures, as the following excerpt about basic protective and safety equipment in the painting trade shows:

Oriane: We are not taught enough [about protective measures]. It's done quickly and the [usual] masks are more like 'Go to work! Did you forget your mask? Well, now we're doing [the job].

Ibrahim: Oh yes, there's that too.

Amal: They don't have time to go back [to the premises]. They are right, it's a waste of time. You go back to the depot just to look for masks...

(...)

Oriane: I feel stupid, clearly (laughs), to be the only one with a mask when everyone else is without a mask, all the other trades that come and go... No, really, I feel stupid when I'm the only one putting on a mask.

[Interview 1]

Everything indicates that the protective measures come up against the temporal constraints of the work, which are quite typical in the construction trades (Jounin, 2009).

5 Conclusion

The COVID policy measures taken in the VET system reveal the special status of apprentices as both workers and learners. Apprentices were given the same relief as students in terms of examinations and teaching courses by vocational school. However, there were also partly assimilated to young workers and, as such subject to the same conditions as adult workers. This

special status is part of a training policy based on a public-private partnership. The exceptional measures enacted during the pandemic concerning the apprenticeship market are a response to this training policy. These measures are justified by the authorities and labour organisations in terms of the high rate of retention in apprenticeship and integration into the labour market. This particular configuration has nevertheless exposed apprentices to work and training conditions that could potentially generate suffering. However, from the media's point of view, the overemphasis on the suffering of young people during the COVID makes invisible what the suffering of apprentices owes to their status. The conversation with the apprentices shows that their suffering during the pandemic is inextricably linked to their particular status. In some cases, the COVID period had accentuated the ordinary suffering associated with their status, particularly among the healthcare assistant apprentices. In other cases, particularly for retail professional apprentices, measures to restrict access to shops have reduced the workload and pressure which is usually a burden on apprentices' health. In all cases, the apprentices' experience during the pandemic reveal a ordinary suffering that has gone unnoticed in the political and media discourse.

Ethics statement

The affiliation institution (SFUVET) for this research did not yet have clearly established ethical provisions. Consequently, this research referred to the fundamental principles of deontology and ethics in research, relying in particular on the SNSF recommendations. To this end, each participant received a consent form at the beginning of the interview, which was dated and signed. The participants received oral explanations on the objectives of the research, the respect of confidentiality and anonymity, as well as the data protection measures (e.g. server protected by an access code).

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Appendix

Chart A

Main measures taken by the Confederation between March 2020 and October 2022

13 March 2020	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Face-to-face activities in compulsory and post-compulsory schools and other educational establishments are prohibited. Examinations whose date has already been set may be held if the necessary protective measures are taken. The competent cantonal authority may, however, grant exceptional exemptions from these bans if the training institution, the organisers or the operator present a protection plan including preventive measures (exclusion of sick persons, protection of persons at risk, hygiene rules by disinfecting hands, masks and distance). - Continuation of business activities, including for apprentices.
16 March 2020	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Companies are obliged, if they can, to use telework. - Shops and markets, restaurants, entertainment establishments, hairdressers must close. Current food shops, small take-away food services (canteens, meal delivery, catering for hotel guests), health care facilities (clinics, hospitals, etc.) may remain open. - The competent cantonal authority may derogate from these prohibitions if there is an overriding public interest in doing so, for example in educational establishments or in the event of supply difficulties, and if the educational establishment or the operator complies with the prevention measures.
21 March 2020	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Employers in the main and secondary construction sectors and employers in industry are obliged to comply with the recommendations of the Federal Office of Public Health regarding hygiene and social distancing. This includes limiting the number of people present on construction sites or in companies accordingly, adapting the organisation of construction sites and the operation of companies, and preventing gatherings of more than five people in break rooms and canteens.
16 April 2020	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Derogation from the provisions on examinations at secondary level I and II (schools, gymnasiums, vocational training establishments) in favour of the guidelines applicable throughout Switzerland, which have been drawn up jointly by the Confederation, the cantons and the organisations of the working world.
24 April 2020	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Face-to-face activities in post-compulsory schools and universities as well as in other educational establishments are prohibited. The FOPH's recommendations on hygiene and social distancing must be respected in the case of authorised face-to-face activities. Examinations in educational establishments may take place if the FOPH's recommendations on hygiene and social distancing and the preventive measures (wearing of masks, distance, etc.) are observed.
27 April 2020	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Hairdressers must be reopened if they have a protection plan. - The cantons must ensure that the inpatient sector of hospitals and clinics has sufficient capacity (e.g. beds and staff) for COVID-19 patients and other urgent examinations and treatments.
11 May 2020	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Reopening of shops (including DIY shops and garden centres) if they have a protection plan. - Resumption of face-to-face teaching in post-compulsory schools and other training establishments, in groups of up to five people.
6 June 2020	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Face-to-face teaching in compulsory schools, post-compulsory schools, universities and other educational institutions is permitted if a protection plan is implemented. The cantons decide whether face-to-face teaching takes place in compulsory schools, post-compulsory schools and cantonal tertiary schools.
19 June 2020	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - End of telework, under the following conditions: <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Operators of installations or establishments accessible to the public, including training establishments, must draw up and implement a protection

	<p>plan. The distance may be disregarded if appropriate protective measures are provided, such as the wearing of a face mask or the presence of adequate partitions. The cantons may grant relief or temporarily limit the number of clients, visitors or participants in training facilities and establishments more strictly.</p> <p>2. The employer shall ensure that employees are able to comply with the FOPH's recommendations on hygiene and distance. If the recommended distance cannot be observed, measures must be taken to implement the STOP principle (substitution, technology, organisation, personnel), including teleworking, physical separation, team separation or the wearing of face masks.</p>
22 June 2020	- End of prevention measures on construction sites and in industry.
29 October 2020	- Prohibition of face-to-face teaching at universities and other educational institutions, except for compulsory schools and post-compulsory institutions.

Chart B

Main cantonal measures to promote VET in the face of COVID

Canton	Measures
Vaud	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - CHF 16 million (2020) to support training companies ready to take on an apprentice at the start of the school year. They can be relieved of half of the salary of their new apprentice during the first year of training. The same benefit has been promised to companies willing to rehire a 2nd or 3rd year apprentice who has lost their place under Covid-19. - The deadline for apprentices to be engaged in 2020-2021 training is extended from 31 July to 15 November. - CHF 3.2 million (2020) to encourage training companies to create networks of companies to share the responsibility and burden of training an apprentice in small and medium-sized companies. Apprentices who lost their jobs during the pandemic period are supported by vocational commissioners and apprentice advisors to ensure that their training can be completed.
Geneva	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - CHF 2.1 million (2020) and 2.3 million (2021) to finance the CHF 10,000 bonus for the creation of a new network of training companies, the payment of the first three months' wages for companies experiencing economic difficulties, and the one-off bonus of CHF 3,000 for all new training companies. - The deadline for apprentices to start training in 2020-2021 has been extended to 31 October 2021. Candidates for an apprenticeship place can attend theoretical courses until they sign a contract, while receiving placement assistance and academic upgrading.
Fribourg	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - CHF 5 million (2020-2023) to finance the first months' salary of a first-year apprentice in the form of a cheque for CHF 1,000, which cannot be accumulated. - CHF 200,000 (2021) for the "last minute" measure aimed at putting young people looking for an apprenticeship in touch with training companies. - CHF 1.8 million (2022) for the extension of existing measures. - The deadline for apprentices to start training is extended to the end of October 2020.
Neuchâtel	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - CHF 2.5 million (2021) to finance a support fund granting between CHF 2,600 and CHF 6,900 for any company in Neuchâtel training a new apprentice.
Valais	- No information.